

OPERATIONS ON INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL CUBIC SOFT MATRICES

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Abstract:

In this paper, we define some operations on internal and external cubic soft matrices. We also characterized some of its algebraic properties.

Key Words: Cubic Soft Sets, Internal Cubic Soft Sets, External Cubic Soft Sets, Fuzzy Matrices & Internal and External Cubic Soft Matrices.

1. Introduction:

The concept of fuzzy set was introduced by Zadeh[12]. He studied their properties on the parallel lines to set theory. Since their many papers on fuzzy sets appeared high lighting the importance of the concept and its applications to logic set theory, group theory, real analysis, measure theory, topology etc.

In 1975, Zedeh[12] introduced a new notion of fuzzy sets viz., internal valued fuzzy subsets, where the values of the membership function are closed interval of numbers instead of a number.

In 1999, Molodstov [8] introduced the novel concept of softsets and established the fundamental results of the new theory. In [3], Jun *et al.* introduced a new notion of cubic set which is a combinations of fuzzy set and interval valued fuzzy set and also investigated several properties of cubic sets.

Fuzzy matrix was introduced by Thomason [11] and the concept of uncertainty was discussed by using fuzzy matrices. Chinnadurai and Barkavi introduced a new concept of cubic soft matrix, interval cubic soft matrix and external cubic soft matrix[2].

In this paper, we define some operations on internal and external cubic soft matrix. We also discuss some basic algebraic properties of cubic soft matrix.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section first we review some basic concepts and definitions.

Definition 2.1 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. A cubic soft set over U is defined to be a pair (Φ, A) where Φ is a mapping from A to $P(U)$ and $A \subseteq E$. Then the pair (Φ, A) can be represented as, $(\Phi, A) = \{\Phi(e)/e \in A\}$ where $\Phi(e) = \{\langle u, \tilde{A}_e(u), \lambda_e(u) \rangle / u \in U, e \in A\}$ is a cubic soft set in which $\tilde{A}_e(u)$ is the interval valued fuzzy set and $\lambda_e(u)$ is a fuzzy set.

Definition 2.2 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. A cubic soft set (Φ, A) over U is said to be an internal cubic soft set if $A_e^-(u) \leq \lambda_e(u) \leq A_e^+(u)$ for all $e \in A$ and for all $u \in U$.

Definition 2.3 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. A cubic soft set (Φ, A) over U is said to be an external cubic soft set if $\lambda_e(u) \notin (A_e^-(u), A_e^+(u))$ for all $e \in A$ and for all $u \in U$.

Definition 2.4 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. For any subsets A and B of E , (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) be cubic soft sets over U .

1. The R-union of (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) is a cubic soft set (H, C) where $C = A \cup B$ and

$$H(e) = \begin{cases} \Phi(e) & \text{if } e \in A/B, \\ \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in B/A, \\ \Phi(e) \cup_R \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

for all $e \in C$. This is denoted by $(H, C) = (\Phi, A) \cup_R (\Gamma, B)$.

2. The R-intersection of (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) is a cubic soft set (H, C) where $C = A \cap B$ and

$$He) = \begin{cases} \Phi(e) & \text{if } e \in A/B, \\ \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in B/A, \\ \Phi(e) \cap_R \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

for all $e \in C$. This is denoted by $(H, C) = (\Phi, A) \cap_R (\Gamma, B)$.

Definition 2.5 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. For any subsets A and B of E , (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) be cubic soft sets over U .

1. The P-union of (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) is a cubic soft set (H, C) where $C = A \cup B$ and

$$He) = \begin{cases} \Phi(e) & \text{if } e \in A/B, \\ \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in B/A, \\ \Phi(e) \cup_p \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

for all $e \in C$. This is denoted by $(H, C) = (\Phi, A) \cup_p (\Gamma, B)$.

2. The P-intersection of (Φ, A) and (Γ, B) is a cubic soft set (H, C) where $C = A \cap B$ and

$$He) = \begin{cases} \Phi(e) & \text{if } e \in A/B, \\ \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in B/A, \\ \Phi(e) \cap_p \Gamma(e) & \text{if } e \in A \cap B \end{cases}$$

for all $e \in C$. This is denoted by $(H, C) = (\Phi, A) \cap_p (\Gamma, B)$.

Definition 2.6 [9] Let U be an initial universal set and E be a set of parameters. The complement of a cubic soft set (Φ, A) over U is denoted by $(\Phi, A)^c$ and defined by

$$(\Phi, A)^c = (\Phi^c, -A) \text{ where } \Phi^c : -A \rightarrow \mathcal{XP}(U) \text{ and } (\Phi, A)^c = \{ \Phi^c(e) / e \in A \} \text{ where } \Phi^c(e) = \left\langle u, \tilde{A}_e^c(u), \lambda_e^c(u) \right\rangle / u \in U, e \in A \}$$

Definition 2.7 [7] A matrix $A = [a_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ is said to be fuzzy matrix if $a_{ij} \in [0, 1], 1 \leq i \leq m$ and $1 \leq j \leq n$.

Definition 2.8 [7] For any two fuzzy matrices $A = [a_{ij}], B = [b_{ij}]$ and a scalar $k \in F$. Then,

- (i) $A + B = [\sup \{a_{ij}, b_{ij}\}] = \vee [a_{ij}, b_{ij}]$.
- (ii) $AB = [\sup \{ \inf \{a_{ij}, b_{ij}\} \}] = \vee \{ \wedge [a_{ij}, b_{ij}] \}$.
- (iii) $kA = [\inf \{k, a_{ij}\}] = \wedge [k, a_{ij}]$.

Definition 2.9 [7] For any fuzzy matrix $A = [a_{ij}]$, the transpose is obtained by interchanging its rows and columns and is denoted by $A^T = [a_{ji}]$ for all i, j .

Definition 2.10 Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_m\}$ be an initial universal set and $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ be a set of parameters. Let $A \subseteq E$. Then cubic soft set (Φ, A) can be expressed in matrix form as

$$A^c = [a_{ij}] = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \cdots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \cdots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \cdots & a_{mn} \end{bmatrix}$$

such that $A^c = [a_{ij}] = \left\langle \tilde{A}_{e_j}^a(u_i), \lambda_{e_j}^a(u_i) \right\rangle = \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle$ which is called an $m \times n$ cubic soft matrix (shortly CS-matrix or CSM) of the cubic soft set (Φ, A) .

According to this definition, a cubic soft set (Φ, A) is uniquely characterized by matrix $[a_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ where $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$.

Example 2.11 Let $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4\}$ is a set of cars and $A = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\}$ is a set of parameters, which stands for mileage, engine and prize respectively. Then cubic soft set is defined as

$$(\Phi, A) = \left\{ \begin{aligned} &[e_1, (u_1, \langle [0.5, 0.8]0.6 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.1, 0.7]0.5 \rangle), (u_3, \langle [0.2, 0.6]0.9 \rangle), (u_4, \langle [0.3, 0.9]0.4 \rangle)], \\ &[e_2, (u_1, \langle [0.2, 0.5]0.3 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.3, 0.6]0.7 \rangle), (u_3, \langle [0.2, 0.7]0.2 \rangle), (u_4, \langle [0.3, 0.5]0.1 \rangle)], \\ &[e_3, (u_1, \langle [0.1, 0.8]0.4 \rangle), (u_2, \langle [0.6, 0.7]0.9 \rangle), (u_3, \langle [0.2, 0.9]0.5 \rangle), (u_4, \langle [0.3, 0.7]0.4 \rangle)]. \end{aligned} \right\}.$$

Then the CS-matrix A^ζ is written as,

$$A^\zeta = \begin{bmatrix} \langle [0.5, 0.8]0.6 \rangle & \langle [0.2, 0.5]0.3 \rangle & \langle [0.1, 0.8]0.4 \rangle \\ \langle [0.1, 0.7]0.5 \rangle & \langle [0.3, 0.6]0.7 \rangle & \langle [0.6, 0.7]0.9 \rangle \\ \langle [0.2, 0.6]0.7 \rangle & \langle [0.2, 0.7]0.2 \rangle & \langle [0.2, 0.9]0.5 \rangle \\ \langle [0.3, 0.9]0.4 \rangle & \langle [0.3, 0.5]0.1 \rangle & \langle [0.3, 0.7]0.4 \rangle \end{bmatrix}.$$

3. Operations on Internal and External Cubic Soft Matrices:

In this section we define operations on internal and external cubic soft matrices and discuss some algebraic properties.

Definition 3.1 [2] Let $A^\zeta = [a_{ij}] \in CSM_{m \times n}$. Then A^ζ is an internal cubic soft matrix (ICSM), if $\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-} \leq \lambda_{ij}^a \leq \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}$ for all i, j .

Definition 3.2 [2] Let $A^\zeta = [a_{ij}] \in CSM_{m \times n}$. Then A^ζ is an external cubic soft matrix (ECSM), if $\lambda_{ij}^a \notin (\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+})$ for all i, j .

Definition 3.3 [2] Let $A^\zeta = \langle [\tilde{A}_{ij}^{a-}, \tilde{A}_{ij}^{a+}], \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^\zeta = \langle [\tilde{B}_{ij}^{b-}, \tilde{B}_{ij}^{b+}], \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \in CSM_{m \times n}$. Then

1. P-union of A^ζ and B^ζ is denoted by $A^\zeta \vee_P B^\zeta$ and defined as $A^\zeta \vee_P B^\zeta = C^\zeta$, if $C^\zeta = [c_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$, where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^c = \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}$ and $\gamma_{ij}^c = \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}$ for all i, j .

2. P-intersection of A^ζ and B^ζ is denoted by $A^\zeta \wedge_P B^\zeta$ and defined as $A^\zeta \wedge_P B^\zeta = C^\zeta$, if $C^\zeta = [c_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$, where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^c = \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}$ and $\gamma_{ij}^c = \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}$ for all i, j .

3. R-union of A^ζ and B^ζ is denoted by $A^\zeta \vee_R B^\zeta$ and defined as $A^\zeta \vee_R B^\zeta = C^\zeta$, if $C^\zeta = [c_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$, where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^c = \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}$ and $\gamma_{ij}^c = \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}$ for all i, j .

4. R-intersection of A^ζ and B^ζ is denoted by $A^\zeta \wedge_R B^\zeta$ and defined as

$A^\zeta \wedge_R B^\zeta = C^\zeta$, if $C^\zeta = [c_{ij}] = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$, where $\tilde{C}_{ij}^c = \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}$ and $\gamma_{ij}^c = \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}$ for all i, j .

Proposition 3.4 Let $A^\zeta, B^\zeta, C^\zeta \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$). Then

(i) $A^\zeta \vee_P A^\zeta = A^\zeta$.

(ii) $A^\zeta \vee_R A^\zeta = A^\zeta$.

(iii) $A^\zeta \wedge_P A^\zeta = A^\zeta$.

(iv) $A^\zeta \wedge_R A^\zeta = A^\zeta$.

Proof. Let $A^\zeta, B^\zeta, C^\zeta \in ICSM_{m \times n}$.

(i) $A^\zeta \vee_P A^\zeta = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} A^\zeta \vee_P A^\zeta &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \\ &= A^\zeta. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $A^\zeta \vee_R A^\zeta = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \vee_R A^{\langle} &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $A^{\langle} \wedge_P A^{\langle} = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \wedge_P A^{\langle} &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

(iv) $A^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle} = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle} &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3.5 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle} \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$). Then

(i) $A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle} = B^{\langle} \vee_P A^{\langle}$.

(ii) $A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle} = B^{\langle} \vee_R A^{\langle}$.

(iii) $A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle} = B^{\langle} \wedge_P A^{\langle}$.

(iv) $A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle} = B^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle}$.

Proof. (i) $A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle} = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle} &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= B^{\langle} \vee_P A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle} = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle} &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= B^{\langle} \vee_R A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle} = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle} &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= B^{\langle} \wedge_P A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

(iv) $A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle} = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle} &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= B^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Note 3.6 In Proposition 3.5, (i) and (iii) are also an ICSM. But (ii) and (iv) are not an ICSM.

Proposition 3.7 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle}, C^{\langle} \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$). Then

- (i) $(A^c \vee_P B^c) \vee_P C^c = A^c \vee_P (B^c \vee_P C^c)$
- (ii) $(A^c \vee_R B^c) \vee_R C^c = A^c \vee_R (B^c \vee_R C^c)$
- (iii) $(A^c \wedge_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c = A^c \wedge_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c)$
- (iv) $(A^c \wedge_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c = A^c \wedge_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c)$

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^c = \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle, C^c = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \in ICSM_{m \times n}$.

Then (i) $(A^c \vee_P B^c) \vee_P C^c = \langle \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$.

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_P B^c) \vee_R C^c &= \langle \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \rangle \vee_P C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \max\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= A^c \vee_P \langle \langle \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= A^c \vee_P (B^c \vee_R C^c) \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $(A^c \vee_R B^c) \vee_R C^c = \langle \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$.

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_R B^c) \vee_R C^c &= \langle \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \rangle \vee_R C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \max\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= A^c \vee_R \langle \langle \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= A^c \vee_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $(A^c \wedge_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c = \langle \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$.

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c &= \langle \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \rangle \wedge_P C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= A^c \wedge_P \langle \langle \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= A^c \wedge_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c) \end{aligned}$$

(iv) $(A^c \wedge_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c = \langle \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle$.

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c &= \langle \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \rangle \wedge_R C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= A^c \wedge_R \langle \langle \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= A^c \wedge_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) \end{aligned}$$

Note 3.8 In Proposition 3.7, (i) and (iii) are also an ICSM. But (ii) and (iv) are not an ICSM.

Proposition 3.9 Let $A^c, B^c \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$). Then

- (i) $(A^c \vee_P B^c)^c = (A^c)^c \wedge_P (B^c)^c$
- (ii) $(A^c \vee_R B^c)^c = (A^c)^c \wedge_R (B^c)^c$

$$(iii) (A^c \wedge_P B^c)^c = (A^c)^c \vee_P (B^c)^c.$$

$$(iv) (A^c \wedge_R B^c)^c = (A^c)^c \vee_R (B^c)^c.$$

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^c = \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \in ICSM_{m \times n}$.

Then (i) $(A^c \vee_P B^c)^c = \langle \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \rangle^c$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_P B^c)^c &= 1 - (A^c \vee_P B^c) \\ &= 1 - \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{1 - \lambda_{ij}^a, 1 - \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \min\{(\tilde{A}_{ij}^a)^c, (\tilde{B}_{ij}^b)^c\}, \min\{(\lambda_{ij}^a)^c, (\mu_{ij}^b)^c\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c)^c \wedge_P (B^c)^c. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $(A^c \vee_R B^c)^c = \langle \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \rangle^c$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_R B^c)^c &= 1 - (A^c \vee_R B^c) \\ &= 1 - \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{1 - \lambda_{ij}^a, 1 - \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \min\{(\tilde{A}_{ij}^a)^c, (\tilde{B}_{ij}^b)^c\}, \max\{(\lambda_{ij}^a)^c, (\mu_{ij}^b)^c\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c)^c \wedge_R (B^c)^c. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $(A^c \wedge_P B^c)^c = \langle \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \rangle^c$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_P B^c)^c &= 1 - (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \\ &= 1 - \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \max\{1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{1 - \lambda_{ij}^a, 1 - \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \max\{(\tilde{A}_{ij}^a)^c, (\tilde{B}_{ij}^b)^c\}, \max\{(\lambda_{ij}^a)^c, (\mu_{ij}^b)^c\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c)^c \vee_P (B^c)^c. \end{aligned}$$

(iv) $(A^c \wedge_R B^c)^c = \langle \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \rangle^c$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_R B^c)^c &= 1 - (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \\ &= 1 - \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \max\{1 - \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, 1 - \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{1 - \lambda_{ij}^a, 1 - \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \max\{(\tilde{A}_{ij}^a)^c, (\tilde{B}_{ij}^b)^c\}, \min\{(\lambda_{ij}^a)^c, (\mu_{ij}^b)^c\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c)^c \vee_R (B^c)^c. \end{aligned}$$

Note 3.10 In Proposition 3.9, (i) and (iii) are also an ICSM. But (ii) and (iv) are not an ICSM.

Theorem 3.11 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$). Then

- (i) $(A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c = (A^c \wedge_P C^c) \vee_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c)$.
- (ii) $(A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_R C^c = (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_P (B^c \wedge_R C^c)$.
- (iii) $(A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_P C^c = (A^c \wedge_P C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_P C^c)$.
- (iv) $(A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c = (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c)$.
- (v) $(A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_P C^c = (A^c \vee_P C^c) \wedge_P (B^c \vee_P C^c)$.

$$(vi) \quad (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_R C^c = (A^c \vee_R C^c) \wedge_P (B^c \vee_R C^c),$$

$$(vii) \quad (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_P C^c = (A^c \vee_P C^c) \wedge_R (B^c \vee_P C^c),$$

$$(viii) \quad (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R C^c = (A^c \vee_R C^c) \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c),$$

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^c = \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle, C^c = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \in ICSM_{m \times n}$.

$$\text{Then (i) } (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \wedge_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_P C^c &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c \wedge_P C^c) \vee_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c). \end{aligned}$$

$$(ii) \quad (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_R C^c = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \wedge_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_R C^c &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_P (B^c \wedge_R C^c). \end{aligned}$$

$$(iii) \quad (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_P C^c = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \wedge_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_P C^c &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c \wedge_P C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_P C^c). \end{aligned}$$

$$(iv) \quad (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \wedge_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R C^c &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c \wedge_R C^c) \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c). \end{aligned}$$

$$(v) \quad (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_P C^c = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \vee_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_P C^c &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c \vee_P C^c) \wedge_P (B^c \vee_P C^c). \end{aligned}$$

$$(vi) \quad (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_R C^c = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \vee_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle.$$

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_R C^c &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\ &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\ &= (A^c \vee_R C^c) \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(vii)} \quad (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_P C^c &= \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \vee_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle. \\
 (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_P C^c &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \vee_P C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\
 &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\
 &= (A^c \vee_P C^c) \wedge_R (B^c \vee_P C^c). \\
 \text{(viii)} \quad (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R C^c &= \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right) \vee_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle. \\
 (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R C^c &= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \rangle \vee_R C^c \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \\
 &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\
 &= (A^c \vee_R C^c) \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c).
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.12 Let $A^c, B^c, C^c \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$). Then

- (i) $A^c \vee_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c) = (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_P (A^c \vee_P C^c)$.
- (ii) $A^c \vee_P (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_R (A^c \vee_P C^c)$.
- (iii) $A^c \vee_R (B^c \wedge_P C^c) = (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_P (A^c \vee_R C^c)$.
- (iv) $A^c \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R (A^c \vee_R C^c)$.
- (v) $A^c \wedge_P (B^c \vee_P C^c) = (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_P (A^c \wedge_P C^c)$.
- (vi) $A^c \wedge_P (B^c \vee_R C^c) = (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_R (A^c \wedge_P C^c)$.
- (vii) $A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_P C^c) = (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_P (A^c \wedge_R C^c)$.
- (viii) $A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R (A^c \wedge_R C^c)$.

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle, B^c = \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle, C^c = \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \in ICSM_{m \times n}$.

Then (i) $A^c \vee_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c) = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \left(\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^c \vee_P (B^c \wedge_P C^c) &= A^c \vee_P \langle \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\
 &= (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_P (A^c \vee_P C^c).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{(ii)} \quad A^c \vee_P (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_P \left(\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^c \vee_P (B^c \wedge_R C^c) &= A^c \vee_P \langle \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\
 &= (A^c \vee_P B^c) \wedge_R (A^c \vee_P C^c).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{(iii)} \quad A^c \vee_R (B^c \wedge_P C^c) = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \left(\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \wedge_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A^c \vee_R (B^c \wedge_P C^c) &= A^c \vee_R \langle \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j \\
 &= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \\
 &= (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_P (A^c \vee_R C^c).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$(iv) \quad A^c \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \left(\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$$

$$A^c \vee_R (B^c \wedge_R C^c) = A^c \vee_R \langle \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \min\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \min\{\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle$$

$$= (A^c \vee_R B^c) \wedge_R (A^c \vee_R C^c).$$

$$(v) \quad A^c \wedge_P (B^c \vee_P C^c) = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \left(\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$$

$$A^c \wedge_P (B^c \vee_P C^c) = A^c \wedge_P \langle \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle$$

$$= (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_P (A^c \wedge_P C^c).$$

$$(vi) \quad A^c \wedge_P (B^c \vee_R C^c) = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_P \left(\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$$

$$A^c \wedge_P (B^c \vee_R C^c) = A^c \wedge_P \langle \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle$$

$$= (A^c \wedge_P B^c) \vee_P (A^c \wedge_P C^c).$$

$$(vii) \quad A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_P C^c) = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \left(\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \vee_P \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$$

$$A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_P C^c) = A^c \wedge_R \langle \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \max\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle$$

$$= (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_P (A^c \wedge_R C^c).$$

$$(viii) \quad A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \left(\langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{C}_{ij}^c, \gamma_{ij}^c \rangle \right)$$

$$A^c \wedge_R (B^c \vee_R C^c) = A^c \wedge_R \langle \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \max\{\tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \min\{\mu_{ij}^b, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle \text{ for all } i, j$$

$$= \langle \max\{\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{C}_{ij}^c\}\}, \min\{\max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \gamma_{ij}^c\}\} \rangle$$

$$= (A^c \wedge_R B^c) \vee_R (A^c \wedge_R C^c).$$

Proposition 3.13 Let $A^c \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$). Then

$$(i) \quad (A^c \vee_P A^c)^T = A^c.$$

$$(ii) \quad (A^c \vee_R A^c)^T = A^c.$$

$$(iii) \quad (A^c \wedge_P A^c)^T = A^c.$$

$$(iv) \quad (A^c \wedge_R A^c)^T = A^c.$$

$$(v) \quad (A^c)^T = A^c.$$

Proof. Let $A^c = \langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \in ICSM_{m \times n}$, and $A^c = \langle \tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \lambda_{ji}^a \rangle$.

$$(i) \left(A^{\langle} \vee_P A^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_P \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(A^{\langle} \vee_P A^{\langle} \right)^T &= \left(\left\langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \lambda_{ji}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T. \end{aligned}$$

$$(ii) \left(A^{\langle} \vee_R A^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \vee_R \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(A^{\langle} \vee_R A^{\langle} \right)^T &= \left(\left\langle \max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \lambda_{ji}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T. \end{aligned}$$

$$(iii) \left(A^{\langle} \wedge_P A^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_P \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(A^{\langle} \wedge_P A^{\langle} \right)^T &= \left(\left\langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \lambda_{ji}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T. \end{aligned}$$

$$(iv) \left(A^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \wedge_R \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(A^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle} \right)^T &= \left(\left\langle \min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{A}_{ij}^a\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a\} \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \lambda_{ji}^a \right\rangle \\ &= \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T. \end{aligned}$$

$$(v) \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle^T \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(A^{\langle} \wedge_R A^{\langle} \right)^T &= \left(\left\langle \tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \lambda_{ji}^a \right\rangle \right)^T \\ &= \left\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \right\rangle \\ &= A^{\langle}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3.14 Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle} \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$). Then

$$(i) \left(A^{\langle} \vee_P B^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T \vee_P \left(B^{\langle} \right)^T.$$

$$(ii) \left(A^{\langle} \vee_R B^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T \vee_R \left(B^{\langle} \right)^T.$$

$$(iii) \left(A^{\langle} \wedge_P B^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T \wedge_P \left(B^{\langle} \right)^T.$$

$$(iv) \left(A^{\langle} \wedge_R B^{\langle} \right)^T = \left(A^{\langle} \right)^T \wedge_R \left(B^{\langle} \right)^T.$$

Proof. Let $A^{\langle}, B^{\langle} \in ICSM_{m \times n}$ (resp. $ECSM_{m \times n}$).

(i) $(A^c \vee_p B^c)^T = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_p \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right)^T$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_p B^c)^T &= \left(\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left(\max\{\tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \tilde{B}_{ji}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ji}^a, \mu_{ji}^b\} \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= (A^c)^T \vee_p (B^c)^T. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) $(A^c \vee_R B^c)^T = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \vee_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right)^T$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \vee_R B^c)^T &= \left(\max\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left(\max\{\tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \tilde{B}_{ji}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ji}^a, \mu_{ji}^b\} \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= (A^c)^T \vee_R (B^c)^T. \end{aligned}$$

(iii) $(A^c \wedge_p B^c)^T = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_p \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right)^T$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_p B^c)^T &= \left(\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left(\min\{\tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \tilde{B}_{ji}^b\}, \min\{\lambda_{ji}^a, \mu_{ji}^b\} \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= (A^c)^T \wedge_p (B^c)^T. \end{aligned}$$

(iv) $(A^c \wedge_R B^c)^T = \left(\langle \tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \lambda_{ij}^a \rangle \wedge_R \langle \tilde{B}_{ij}^b, \mu_{ij}^b \rangle \right)^T$ for all i, j .

$$\begin{aligned} (A^c \wedge_R B^c)^T &= \left(\min\{\tilde{A}_{ij}^a, \tilde{B}_{ij}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ij}^a, \mu_{ij}^b\} \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= \left(\min\{\tilde{A}_{ji}^a, \tilde{B}_{ji}^b\}, \max\{\lambda_{ji}^a, \mu_{ji}^b\} \right)^T \text{ for all } i, j \\ &= (A^c)^T \wedge_R (B^c)^T. \end{aligned}$$

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